

An Observational Comparative Study of Association of Serum Ferritin with Various Components of Metabolic Syndrome and Insulin ResistanceVikash Kumar¹, Kanhaiya Lal Sharma², Prakash Keswani³, Sanjay Kumawat⁴¹M.D. General medicine, S.M.S. Medical College & Attached Group of Hospitals, Jaipur (Rajasthan)²M.D. General medicine, S.M.S. Medical College & Attached Group of Hospitals, Jaipur (Rajasthan)³Senior Professor & Unit head, Department of Medicine, S.M.S. Medical College & Attached Group of Hospitals, Jaipur (Rajasthan)⁴M.D. General medicine, S.M.S. Medical College & Attached Group of Hospitals, Jaipur (Rajasthan)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: The metabolic syndrome is a concept rather than a disease in itself. It is a prothrombotic and pro-inflammatory state that is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes mellitus. Serum Ferritin is a well-established biomarker used to assess degree of inflammation in various clinical conditions. Hence, aim of our study was to explore the association of serum ferritin levels with the components of metabolic syndrome (abdominal obesity, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and hyperglycaemia) and insulin resistance and comparison with healthy controls.

Material and Method: Present study was conducted at SMS Medical College, Jaipur from April 2021 to August 2022. 30 cases of metabolic syndrome (Group 1) and 30 healthy controls (Group 2) were enrolled. Detailed history, clinical examination and anthropometric measurements were taken of all the subjects of both groups. Serum ferritin was measured and its association with various components of metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance was investigated. Study parameters were analyzed by statistical tests including student's t-test, X² analysis, multiple regression analysis.

Results: Serum ferritin level was considerably ($p < 0.001$) higher in cases (mean 552.9 ± 464.44 mcg/L) compared to controls (mean 212.77 ± 74.07 mcg/L) and it has significant correlation with waist circumference ($p < 0.01$), neck circumference ($p < 0.02$), fasting blood glucose ($p < 0.002$), fasting insulin level ($p < 0.05$), level of insulin resistance (HOMA IR) ($p < 0.01$), S. Triglycerides ($p < 0.05$) and S. VLDL ($p < 0.04$) in the case group when analyzed by linear regression analysis.

Conclusion: Our findings based on community-based data showed that higher serum ferritin levels though in the normal range are associated with obesity, components of the metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance. These observations not only suggest a good correlation with serum ferritin, but also emphasize that serum ferritin can also be used as a marker for insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome.

Keywords: Obesity, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Metabolic Syndrome.

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Introduction

Worldwide prevalence of metabolic syndrome (MetS) ranges from 20% to 25% [1]. The prevalence was significantly higher in Eastern Mediterranean Region and America. MetS is a growing epidemic in India affecting more than one-third population in large cities.

Various population based studies have been done to quantify the burden of metabolic syndrome in Indian population, according to the results of these studies 10-30% of Indians are suffering from Metabolic syndrome because of lifestyle changes, behavioural habits and increasing urban population. [2] Metabolic syndrome (Met S) is a cluster of risk factors that are associated with increased risk of

cardiovascular diseases, cerebrovascular diseases, and Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). MetS has been associated with a 5-fold increase in the risk of development of Type 2 diabetes mellitus and 2-fold increased risk of developing the cardiovascular disease over the next 5–10 years. [3]

Insulin resistance which represents a reduced physiological response of the peripheral tissues to the action of insulin is a major finding in T2DM and metabolic syndrome. [4] There are strong links between obesity, insulin resistance, and components of the metabolic syndrome. Chronic low-grade inflammation has been implicated in the

pathophysiology of these three intertwined entities. [5]

Ferritin is one of the key proteins regulating iron homeostasis, is a widely available clinical biomarker to evaluate iron status and for detecting iron deficiency. However, growing evidence has shown that even moderately increased iron stores represented by high-normal ferritin concentrations are associated with diabetes. [6]

It has also been demonstrated that ferritin is related to various metabolic diseases, such as obesity diabetes, insulin resistance, MetS and T2DM [7]. The pathophysiology underlying the relationship between ferritin and MetS is not fully understood. One possible explanation is that excessive iron can induce oxidative stress that plays a key role in iron-mediated tissue damage. Although the molecular events of iron-mediated tissue damage have not been fully elucidated, mitochondria are the targets of iron-mediated damage and iron may be preferentially toxic to cells with high mitochondrial activity, such as hepatocytes and pancreatic beta cells. Impaired mitochondrial activity has been observed in the insulin-resistant offspring of patients with type 2 diabetes and mitochondrial defect can also lead to the metabolic syndrome. Therefore, iron-induced oxidative stress with mitochondrial dysfunction could be one of the underlying mechanisms in these metabolic disorders.

With this background, the present study was conducted to assess serum ferritin levels in patients of metabolic syndrome and compare with healthy controls and to gauge the association of serum ferritin with complications of metabolic syndrome at presentation.

Material and Method

This hospital based observational comparative study was done in the department of medicine, SMS Medical College, Jaipur from April 2021 to August 2022 after obtaining permission from the institutional ethics committee. 30 consecutive patients of metabolic syndrome aged more than 18

years were recruited in case group by using International Diabetes Federation criteria for metabolic syndrome i.e. increased waist circumference (south Asian cut-off ≥ 90 cm for men and ≥ 80 cm for women), plus any two of the following: Triglycerides ≥ 150 mg/dl or on treatment for Triglycerides, HDL cholesterol < 40 mg/dl in men and < 50 mg/dl in women or on treatment for HDL, systolic BP > 130 or diastolic BP > 85 mm Hg or on treatment for hypertension and fasting plasma glucose ≥ 100 mg/dl or on treatment for type 2 diabetes were taken as cases (n=30). 30 healthy individuals between 18 to 80 years were included in control group. Individual with acute infection, chronic inflammatory disease such as IBD and inflammatory arthritis, h/o blood transfusion in last 6 months, anemia, Clinical evidence of haemochromatosis, Endocrine disorder like thyroid disease or Individuals not willing to give consent were excluded from study group.

All participants after their written informed consent underwent detailed physical and clinical examination. Their anthropometric measurements like height, weight, BMI, waist circumference and neck circumference were taken. All the participants were further subjected to following investigations including complete blood count, fasting blood sugar and lipid profile, liver and renal function test.

Statistical Analysis

All data were analysed statistically and comparison made using students t test. Multiple regression analyses were performed with Serum Ferritin concentrations as the dependent variable, and significant parameters (Waist circumference, neck circumference, SBP, DBP, FBS, Fasting Insulin Level, HOMA IR, TG, cholesterol, HDL, LDL, VLDL) as the independent variables. All statistical analyses were performed taking level of significance at p-value < 0.05 .

Results

In this study, 30 patients with metabolic syndrome were included in case group while 30 healthy persons were taken as control group.

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic, Anthropometric and Blood Pressure parameters in both groups.

Parameters	Cases(Group1) (n=30)	Controls(Group2) (n=30)	p-value
	Mean	Mean	
Age (years)	58.93 \pm 12.26	55.03 \pm 12.44	0.226
Sex			> 0.05
Female	13(43.3%)	12(40%)	
Male	17(56.7%)	18(60%)	
Height (m)	1.61 \pm 0.09	1.64 \pm 0.11	0.142
Weight (kg)	84.97 \pm 9.05	65.37 \pm 10.83	<0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	33.16 \pm 2.19	24.20 \pm 2.46	<0.001
Waist circumference (cm)	102.87 \pm 5.19	79.67 \pm 7.98	<0.001
Neck circumference (cm)	42.03 \pm 3.08	37.10 \pm 1.35	<0.001
SBP (mmHg)	134.07 \pm 9.27	119.73 \pm 9.38	<0.001
DBP (mmHg)	86.20 \pm 6.75	74.73 \pm 8.08	<0.001

In present study difference in age and height of case and control was statistically insignificant (P-value >0.05). The mean age and height among Group 1 was 58.93±12.26 years and 1.6±0.09 meters respectively. While among Group 2 mean age and height was 55.03±12.44 years and 1.64±0.11 meters respectively. These observations suggest that age and height of both Group 1 and Group 2 was matched. We found slightly higher percentage of metabolic syndrome in male population as compared to female population. Out of total 30 patients with metabolic syndrome 17 (56.7%) were male. The difference in the sex distribution of case and

control was found to be statistically insignificant (P-value >0.05). While comparing Anthropometric measurements including weight, BMI, neck circumference and Waist circumference among both groups, we found that all these measurements were significantly higher in cases than controls which was statistically significant (P-value <0.05). Group 1 patients had higher mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure than Group 2, which was statistically significant (P-value <0.05), these results were in line with expectation that systolic and diastolic BP of patients with MetS was higher than the healthy controls.

Table 2: Comparison of various metabolic syndrome parameters, Fasting Insulin Levels, HOMA IR score and Serum Ferritin in both groups

Parameters	Cases(Group 1) (n=30)	Controls(Group2) (n=30)	p-value
	Mean	Mean	
Fasting blood glucose (mg/dl)	150.47±32.92	86.17±6.19	<0.001
Fasting insulin level (µIU/ml)	7.26±4.58	2.96±0.90	<0.001
HOMA IR	2.66±1.72	0.64±0.22	<0.001
Serum Ferritin(mcg/L)	552.9±464.44	212.77±74.07	<0.001
TG (mg/dl)	157.03±33.61	71.57±19.55	<0.001
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	204.70±33.59	115.40±37.23	<0.001
HDL (mg/dl)	42.83±10.39	53.40±13.18	0.001
LDL (mg/dl)	123.70±44.09	30.80±15.03	<0.001
VLDL (mg/dl)	39.93±8.37	26.83±6.24	<0.001

The values of fasting blood glucose, fasting insulin levels, HOMA IR score and serum ferritin are found to be statistically significant high in cases of Metabolic Syndrome as compared with controls. (p-Value< 0.001). While analysing the results of all the components of lipid profile by using sample t-test, it was found statistically significant (P-value <0.05) relation between both groups in reference to all components of Lipid Profile.

Table 3: Correlation of serum ferritin (dependent variable) with waist circumference, neck circumference, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, fasting blood glucose, fasting insulin levels, various lipid parameters and HOMA IR

Components	Correlation with Seum Ferritin (In case group: 30)	Correlation with Seum Ferritin (In control group: 30)
	p value	p value
Waist circumference	0.01	0.65
Neck circumference	0.02	0.29
SBP	0.17	0.35
DBP	0.54	0.97
Fasting blood glucose	0.002	0.006
Fasting insulin level	0.05	0.04
TG	0.05	0.07
Cholesterol	0.02	0.04
HDL	0.85	0.97
LDL	0.89	0.23
VLDL	0.04	0.59
HOMA IR	0.01	0.03

Multiple linear regression analysis in case group showed that Serum Ferritin values are significantly correlated with neck circumference, waist circumference, fasting blood glucose, fasting insulin levels, HOMA IR, triglycerides, total cholesterol and VLDL. However, serum ferritin did not significantly correlate with systolic/diastolic BP and LDL and

HDL. While, in control group, multiple linear regression showed ferritin was statistically not correlated with neck circumference, waist circumference, systolic/diastolic BP and VLDL, LDL and HDL, however ferritin was correlated statistically with fasting blood sugar, fasting insulin level, cholesterol and HOMA IR.

Discussion

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) is state of health that includes clusters of condition which are responsible for increased risk of diabetes, stroke and cardiovascular disease. Widely accepted pathophysiology of metabolic syndrome is insulin resistance and low grade inflammation. The present study was designed to explore the association of serum ferritin levels with various components of metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance.

In present study, we observed male predominance and majority of patients (40%) with MetS were between the age of 65-84 years with mean age of 58.93 ± 12.26 years. Our results were similar to the study conducted by Eunok P et al. [8] they found that Metabolic syndrome shows an association with advanced age for both men and women ($P < .001$ for both), with greater prevalence of metabolic syndrome in young and middle-aged men than in women, these patterns were reversed in people 60 years or older. In our study the mean BMI of cases was significantly higher than that of controls (33.16 ± 2.19 vs 24.20 ± 2.46). Similar results were also observed by Al-Bachir M et al. [9], they used BMI to screen of the presence of metabolic syndrome.

We found that in Group 1, both waist and neck circumference (102.87 ± 5.19 and 42.03 ± 3.08) shows higher values than in Group 2 (79.67 ± 7.98 and 37.10 ± 1.35) and it was statistically significant (P -value < 0.05). Our results were in accordance to the study conducted by Huang Y et al. [10] They also observed that all anthropometric parameters for obesity, including traditional parameters (BMI, WC and WHR) and novel parameters (Product of waist and neck circumference-PWNC and NC), were higher (all $P < 0.01$) in the metabolic syndrome group than in the non-metabolic syndrome group in both genders.

In present study mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure was higher in Group 1 (134.07 ± 9.27 and 86.20 ± 6.75 respectively) as compared to Group 2 (119.73 ± 9.38 and 74.73 ± 8.08 respectively). Our results were similar with the study conducted by Stanley S Fanklin et al. [11] They found that more than 85% of those with metabolic syndrome even in the absence of diabetes, have elevated blood pressure or hypertension.

We also assessed various parameters like fasting blood glucose levels and fasting insulin level and found that in Group 1, fasting blood glucose (150.47 ± 32.92) shows higher value than in Group 2 (86.17 ± 6.19) and similarly mean fasting insulin level (7.26 ± 4.58) in Group 1 shows higher value than in Group 2 (2.96 ± 0.9).

Various studies have shown that increased fasting insulin levels are associated with the prevalence of

metabolic syndrome, which may be due to its representativeness of insulin resistance. [12] We also observed that in Group 1, HOMA IR (2.66 ± 1.72) had higher value than in Group 2 (0.64 ± 0.22). Gayoso-Diz P et al [13] also conducted a cross-sectional study to find the association between MetS and insulin resistance (HOMA IR) and found that patients with metabolic syndrome has significantly higher HOMA IR (P -value < 0.05) as compared to healthy controls.

In present study TG, Total Cholesterol, LDL and VLDL levels were higher in Group 1 (157.03 ± 33.61 , 204.70 ± 33.59 , 123.70 ± 44.09 , 39.93 ± 8.37 mg/dl respectively) than in Group 2 (71.57 ± 19.55 , 115.40 ± 37.23 , 30.80 ± 15.03 , 26.83 ± 6.24 mg/dl respectively) while mean value of HDL was higher in group 2 (53.40 ± 13.18) than group 1 (42.83 ± 10.39). Similar results were found in study conducted by Kawamoto R. et al [14].

Various inflammatory markers including Serum Ferritin have been evaluated in metabolic syndrome. In our study we found that mean level of serum ferritin was 552.9 mcg/L in patients with MetS while it was 212.77 mcg/L in healthy subjects.

These findings success that patients with MetS have higher values of serum ferritin (p value < 0.05) which was statistically significant. Shrey Kumar Srivastav et al. [15] also showed similar results that serum ferritin was significantly elevated in patients of metabolic syndrome at 224.04 ± 53.12 compared with healthy controls at 68.9 ± 56 (p -value < 0.001).

In our study Multiple linear regression analysis was done which showed that Serum Ferritin values are significantly correlated with neck circumference, waist circumference, fasting blood glucose, fasting insulin levels, HOMA IR, triglycerides, total cholesterol and VLDL (P -value < 0.05). However, no significant correlation was observed between serum ferritin and systolic and diastolic BP, LDL and HDL.

Meghana.K.Padwal.et al. [16] also concluded that increased concentration of serum ferritin in metabolic syndrome, though in the normal range, on the higher side of normal was associated with insulin resistance and components of the metabolic syndrome, suggesting its role as a promising biomarker.

Chand MR.et.al [17] conducted a cross-sectional study in India and found that mean serum ferritin level was significantly higher in the subjects with MetS (123.9 vs 59.02 ; $p < 0.0001$). A statistically significant positive correlation was found between serum ferritin and waist hip ratio, triglyceride, BMI and HOMA IR ($r = 0.49$, $p < 0.0001$; $r = 0.50$, $p < 0.0001$; $r = 0.47$, $p < 0.0001$ and $r = 0.54$, $p < 0.0001$ respectively) and an inverse correlation was found

between serum ferritin and serum HDL levels ($r = -0.46$, $p < 0.0001$). They also commented that serum ferritin may be used as a marker of inflammation for assessment of insulin resistance and early intervention.

Elevated serum ferritin reflects systemic inflammation in addition to increased body iron stores, It could potentially be used as a screening biomarker to detect those who are at risk of developing the metabolic syndrome and in early stages of the disease that can still be reversed by targeted preventive measures.

Conclusion

From the findings of our study we can conclude that metabolic syndrome is associated with significantly increased serum ferritin though in the normal limits which can be used as a follow up and risk assessment measure in subjects with metabolic risk factors and also aid in early intervention against cardiovascular risk factors.

This study extends the available information for serum ferritin to a role as a biomarker of non-infectious conditions, namely the metabolic and cardiovascular arena. Moreover, further studies are required to investigate the pathophysiological mechanisms of increased serum ferritin levels in patients with MetS and its potential to identify individuals at risk of cardiovascular and chronic metabolic disease.

Limitations of the study

Smaller sample size belonging to a particular geographic region was notable limitations of our study. Also because of the cross-sectional design causal relationship of serum ferritin with metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance could not be inferred.

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